

ORGANIC REACTIONS WITH POLYPHOSPHORIC ACID. PART IV.
INTRAMOLECULAR ACYLATION WITH LACTONES:
cyclopent-enones FROM γ -LACTONES*

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It has been demonstrated that the intramolecular acylation of suitably constituted γ -lactones to yield *cyclopent-enones* is best carried out with polyphosphoric acid.

A possible mechanism for the formation of γ -lactones by the action of alkylmagnesium halides on γ -keto-esters has been discussed.

Of the several routes available for the synthesis of *cyclopent-enones* (cf. Raphael in Rodd's "Chemistry of Carbon Compounds", Elsevier Publishing Co., Amsterdam, 1953, Vol. IIA, p. 95), the one utilising intramolecular acylation with lactones has certain attractive features. Apparently, Maschmeijer (Fr.P. 765, 515/1934; D.R.P. 667,156/1938; cf. Plattner and Pfau, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1937, 20, 1474) was the first to record such a conversion, when he showed that undeca-lactone on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid yielded 2-hexyl*cyclopent-enone*. Frank *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 4; 1948, 70, 79; 1951, 73, 724) later carried out the conversion of suitably constituted lactones to *cyclopent-enones* by flash-distilling them over phosphorus pentoxide. This procedure has been utilised by others in synthesis (La Forge and Barthel, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1945, 10, 222; Sen Gupta and Datta, *this Journal*, 1948, 25, 213; Gupta and Deshapande, *ibid.*, 1953, 30, 23). A modification of the above method, which involves refluxing the lactone with P_2O_5 in a hydrocarbon solvent, has been preferred by some investigators (Ansell and Hey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2875; Mathieson, *ibid.*, 1951, 177), while Rothstein and Ficini (*Compt. rend.*, 1952, 234, 1694) treated the lactone with P_2O_5 under reduced pressure. The conversion of lactones to *cyclopent-enones* has also been achieved by the zinc chloride-acetic acid-acetic anhydride reagent (Johnson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1360, 1366; Mathieson, *loc. cit.*). Recently, excellent yields in the conversion of lactones to substituted 2-*cyclopent-enones* on heating with silica gel have been claimed (Bowles, U.S.P. 2, 623, 071/1952).

The above-mentioned procedures involving P_2O_5 result in a heterogeneous reaction mixture and furnish the desired *cyclopent-enones* in only moderate yields (20-50%). It was argued that a homogeneous reaction mixture obtainable with polyphosphoric acid (PPA) might result in superior yields. This has actually been found to be the case, and the present communication describes these results.

γ -Lactones

The γ -lactones of type (I) required for this investigation were prepared by the action of the requisite alkylmagnesium halide on ethyl laevulinate (Cason *et al.*, *Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1765 and the references cited therein; Arnold and

Working up of the reaction mixture with an acid will generate the $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated acid from (B). From these considerations it can be deduced that a lower temperature of reaction and a less ionising reaction medium should favour the termination of the reaction at the lactone stage. This is well demonstrated by the work of Cason *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), who have prepared γ -lactones by this method in high yields.

cyclopentenones

On treatment with PPA the γ -lactones (I) were smoothly converted into the cyclopentenones (II) in excellent yields. Table I depicts in a comparative manner the yields of the cyclopentenones as obtained by the P_2O_5 and PPA methods.

(II)

- $$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{a: R = Et} \\ \text{b: R = } n\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7 \\ \text{c: R = } n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9 \\ \text{d: R = } n\text{-C}_5\text{H}_{11} \\ \text{e: R = } n\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{13} \end{array} \right.$$

TABLE I

<i>cyclopentenone</i> (II).	PPA method,	% Yield by	P_2O_5 method,
a	90-92		--
b	92-97		32*
c	92-95		30†
d	92-95		50‡ 62‡
e	92-94		63††

* Frank *et al.* (1948, *loc. cit.*).

‡‡ Frank *et al.* (1944, *loc. cit.*).

†† Gupta and Deshapande (*loc. cit.*).

† La Forge and Barthel (*loc. cit.*).

‡ Rothstein and Ficini (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting and boiling points are uncorrected. The ultraviolet spectra were measured in 95% ethanolic solution on a Beckman DU spectrophotometer. The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones were prepared by the sulphuric acid method and the semicarbazones by the pyridine method.

γ -Methyl- γ -alkylbutyrolactones (I).—In a special apparatus the requisite Grignard reagent was prepared from magnesium (2.43 g., 0.1 g. atom), alkyl bromide (0.015 M) and anhydrous ether (60 c.c.). Two-thirds of the ether was distilled off, the residue

diluted with dry, thiophene-free benzene (40 c.c.) and the solution forced by N_2 pressure into a dropping funnel, fitted to a 3-necked flask carrying a stirrer and containing ethyl laevulinate (14.4 g., 0.1 M) and benzene (100 c.c.). The Grignard reagent was added dropwise with stirring at -10 to 0° during 2 hours. After stirring for an additional $\frac{1}{2}$ hour at the same temperature, the product was poured on ice and H_2SO_4 (C.P., 10 c.c.) and worked up as described by Cason *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). The properties of the lactones, thus prepared, are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Lactone (I).	B.P.	n_D^{20} .	Yield.	Lit. (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	B.P./ n_D/t .	Yield.
a	126-27°/20 mm.	1.4397	55%	Cason <i>et al.</i>	128-29°/15 mm	73.3%
b	118-19°/8	1.4423	60	Frank <i>et al.</i> (1948)	85-87°/2 mm 1.4452/20°	60
c	129-31°/13	1.4447	60	LaForge & Barthel	98-100°/2 mm 1.4478/23°	...
d	159-60°/18	1.4460	60	Frank <i>et al.</i> (1944)	120-25°/4-5 mm 1.4487/20°	31
e	165-67°/12.5	1.4482	62	Gupta & Deshapande	146-48°/12 mm	23

3-Methyl-2-alkyl- Δ^2 -cyclopenten-1-one (II): *General Procedure.*—To PPA (from P_2O_5 , 20 g. and 85% syrupy phosphoric acid 12 c.c. Sukh Dev, *loc. cit.*, 1955) maintained at 97° (boiling water-bath) the γ -lactone (0.02 M) was added, well-mixed with a glass rod and the coloured reaction mixture heated at the same temperature (with occasional mixing) under anhydrous conditions for $2\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The deep red product, while still hot, was poured on ice (*ca.* 200 g.) and after the complex had decomposed, the organic material was taken in petroleum ether (50 c.c. $\times$ 4), washed with water (40 c.c.), brine (40 c.c. $\times$ 2) and dried (Na_2SO_4). The solvent was carefully fractionated off and the crude ketone, thus obtained, was rectified under vacuum. The relevant data are given below:

3-Methyl-2-ethyl- Δ^2 -cyclopenten-1-one (IIa): b. p. 95-96°/18 mm, 86-87°/10 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4780; λ_{max} 234 m μ (ϵ 13,200). (Found: C, 77.3; H, 9.8. $C_8H_{12}O$ requires C, 77.4; H, 9.7%).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones* crystallised from alcohol in deep red needles, m.p. 186°. (Found: N, 18.2. $C_{14}H_{16}O_4N_4$ requires N, 18.4%).

3-Methyl-2-n-propyl- Δ^2 -cyclopenten-1-one (IIb): b.p. 105°/17 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4775; *semicarbazone* (white crystalline nodules from alcohol) m. p. 210-11° (Hunsdiecker, *Ber.*, 1942, 75, 455, records b.p. 94.5°/11.5 mm, m.p. of semicarbazone, 212°).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones* was obtained in deep red flat needles from alcohol, m.p. 182°. (Found: N, 17.4. $C_{15}H_{18}O_4N_4$ requires N, 17.6%).

3-Methyl-2-n-butyl- Δ^2 -cyclopenten-1-one (IIc) (*Dihydrocinerone*): b.p. 124-25°/20 mm, 115-16°/10 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4775; λ_{max} 234 m μ (ϵ 12730); *semicarbazone* (white microcrystalline powder from alcohol) m.p. 191-92°; *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones* (red,

long flat needles from alcohol) m.p. 153-5° (LaForge and Barthel, *loc. cit.*, record b.p. 107°/17 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4798; m.p. of semicarbazone, 191.5-92.5°, m.p. of 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, 154-55°).

3-Methyl-2-n-amyl- Δ^2 -cyclopenten-1-one (IIId) (Dihydrojasnone, Tetrahydropythrone): b.p. 138-39°/20 mm, 127-28°/10 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4760; semicarbazone (white, microcrystalline powder from alcohol) m.p. 175-76°; 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (bright red needles from alcohol) m.p. 123° (Treff and Werner, *Ber.*, 1933, 66, 1525, record b.p. 101-102°/5 mm, n_D^{20} 1.48107; m.p. of semicarbazone 175-76°. Crombie - *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3563, record m.p. of the 2:4 dinitrophenylhydrazone as 122°).

3-Methyl-2-n-hexyl- Δ^2 -cyclopenten-1-one (IIe): b.p. 145-47°/20 mm, 137-38°/10 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4735; λ_{max} 234 m μ (ϵ 12060) (Hunsdiecker, *loc. cit.*, records b.p. 142°/18 mm).

The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone on crystallisation from alcohol furnished red needles, m.p. 135°. (Found: N, 15.3. $C_{18}H_{24}O_4N_4$ requires N, 15.5%).

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